

“Exploring Students’ Perceptions on Need for Digital Citizenship through Life Skills Training “

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ABSTRACT

Digital citizenship emerges as a crucial component of human life, still many students lack the necessary wisdom to use the internet responsibly, safely, and productively. The major aim of this study is to explore students’ perception regarding the need for life skills training to promote digital citizenship. Data was collected through a survey conducted among 60 postgraduate social work students, using purposive sampling. The findings of this empirical study highlight a positive perception among students toward life skills training, highlighting its importance and suggesting relevant methodologies and topics to be included in such training programs.

Keywords: *Life Skills Training, Digital Citizenship, Student Perceptions, Digital Literacy, Holistic Education.*

INTRODUCTION

The fast-growing digital world has transformed the patterns of interaction, learning, and engagement /-in the life of students. While technological transformation provides with immense opportunities, it also comes with challenges such as cyberbullying, digital distraction, privacy breaches, digital addiction etc. In this scenario the concept of digital citizenship which insist on using technology both responsibly and ethically seeks importance.

NEED TO CREATE DIGITAL CITIZENSHIP AWARENESS

Digital citizenship is just not merely about accessing digital tools, but it is about the

developing the attitude to use technology wisely, ensuring safety, respecting others, and contributing positively to the digital space. Students lack awareness on cybersecurity threats such as hacking, phishing, identity theft, and malware attacks. The increasing trends of Cyberbullying, online harassment, and digital misinformation are concerns in the digital world. Fake news, inappropriate content sharing, and privacy breaches are some of the misuses of social media. The risks of data breaches and misuse happens due to unsafe sharing of personal information in online platform. Students involve themselves in plagiarism, copyright violations, and unethical online practices

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due to lack of knowledge. This improper use of technology results in impacting the students' mental health and well-being due excessive screen time, digital addiction, and social media pressure impact.

Digital citizenship education becomes a solution to helps students understand the proper internet and technological usage. The safe online practices such as strong passwords, recognizing phishing emails to be safe from cybercrimes, critical thinking and media literacy and differentiating between reliable and misleading information are a part of digital citizenship. It promotes knowledge of secure online behaviour, respect intellectual property rights, cyber laws, and digital etiquette. Digital citizenship also helps in promoting healthy digital habits, time management, and self-regulation during online engagement. Strong digital competencies and ethical online behaviour is essential for developing professionalism and digital skills needed for future careers. DQ framework (The world's first global standards for digital literacy, digital skills and digital readiness) identifies digital citizenship skills as Digital citizen identity, Privacy management, critical thinking, Digital footprint management, digital empathy, Cyber security management, Cyberbullying management and screen time management. (*8 Digital Life Skills All Children Need - and a Plan for Teaching Them | World Economic Forum, n.d.*)

LIFE SKILLS IN PROMOTING DIGITAL CITIZENSHIP

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines life skills as “The abilities for

adaptive and positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life.” The World Health Organization (WHO) identifies 10 Core Life Skills such as Self-awareness, Critical thinking, Decision-making, Problem-solving, Effective communication, Interpersonal relationships, Empathy, Managing emotions, Coping with stress and Creative thinking.

Role of life skills in digital citizenship is crucial for fostering responsible, ethical, and effective use of digital technologies. Life skills help students to develop competencies to navigate online spaces safely, make informed decisions, and engage positively in digital communities. this skills enhancement helps to balance online interactions with real-world responsibilities, by making them understand the implications of their actions in digital environments. Integration of these life skills in digital platform can empower individuals to become responsible digital citizens. This will help in safeguarding digital well-being to maximize the benefits of technology usage. This study explores perception of students about the need for developing digital citizenship through life skills training. Through which the research seeks to highlight the significance of integrating life skills and digital citizenship education into academic curricula. The findings aim to provide insights into effective strategies for fostering ethical and responsible digital behaviour among students.

CORE LIFE SKILLS AND THEIR ROLE IN DIGITAL CITIZENSHIP:

- **Critical Thinking:** Enables individuals to assess and evaluate digital content, helping them identify credible sources, recognize misinformation, and make well-informed decisions. by Encouraging responsible consumption and dissemination of information online.
- **Communication:** Helps individuals engage in positive, respectful, and effective communication in online by promoting healthy online dialogue which will reduce the chances of cyberbullying and supports constructive digital discussions.
- **Ethical Decision-Making:** Teaches individuals to understand the ethical implications of their actions, such as respecting intellectual property, protecting privacy, and ensuring online safety to foster responsible digital behaviour and ensure respect for others' rights and dignity in the digital world.
- **Problem-Solving:** Develops the ability to identify and address digital challenges, such as cybersecurity threats, privacy concerns, or conflicts in online spaces through proactive engagement with enhanced personal digital security.
- **Self-Regulation and Time Management:** Helps individuals balance their online and offline lives, preventing overuse of digital technologies to promote digital well-being and responsible time management in the digital world.
- **Collaboration:** Encourages individuals to work together and share

knowledge in collaborative digital platforms by promoting shared learning experiences in online spaces.

- **Empathy and Respect:** Encourages understanding and consideration for others' views and emotions while interacting in digital spaces which can prevent online harassment and promotes inclusion, leading to a more respectful and diverse digital environment.

Life skills training to inculcate digital citizenship is suggested as a solution. This study investigates how students view the necessity of life skills training in promoting digital citizenship. The study emphasizes critical thinking, decision-making, communication, emotional intelligence, and other vital life skills as the core element for responsible internet use.

PROMOTING CYBER AWARENESS AMONG STUDENTS

Understanding students' perceptions of online safety and cyber ethics is crucial in developing effective educational programs that promote responsible digital behaviour. Research indicates that while many students are aware of cyber threats, there is often a gap between this awareness and the adoption of safe online practices. A study at Purdue University revealed that students even though were able to recognize various cyber threats, continued to engage in potentially unsafe online activities by exposing the misconceptions about online security and also to educate more about the cyber-threats and cyber-attacks that can put students at risk.(Gonzalez, 2022)

Studies indicates that students often lack

a comprehensive understanding of cyber ethics, leading to behaviours such as unauthorized access or misuse of information systems hence recommends for aggressive awareness campaigns to ensure students and faculty become aware of acceptable and unacceptable online behaviour in order to safeguard the integrity. (Aderibigbe, 2021)

Students Awareness of Digital Rights & Responsibilities can help them to Protect themselves from cyber threats and online exploitation. Encourages responsible digital behaviour and ethical online interactions. This can also help in creating a safe and inclusive digital environment by promoting digital literacy and awareness of legal frameworks governing online activities to ensure the freedom of speech while preventing harm caused by misinformation or cyber harassment.

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

With the rise of digital technology, students' online usage is often without proper awareness of digital etiquettes, privacy, and security. Even though there are already programs for digital literacy, there is only limited research available on importance of life skills to enhance digital citizenship, especially in the Indian context. It was also felt important to understand the student's point of view about the promotion of digital citizenship. Hence this study aims to bridge this gap in exploring students' perceptions on the need for digital citizenship training through life skills training approach.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Digital citizenship frame works

1. **Ribble's Nine Elements of Digital Citizenship (ISTE Framework)** proposed a widely accepted framework consisting of nine elements categorized into three main areas: Respect (Law, Access, and Digital Etiquette) Protect (Digital Rights & Responsibilities, Security, and Health & Wellness) and Educate (Digital Literacy, Communication, and Commerce). (*ISTE | Essential Elements of Digital Citizenship | ISTE*, n.d.).
2. **UNESCO's Digital kids Asia -Pacific framework for education** emphasizes five domains of digital citizenship Digital literacy the capacity to seek for, assess, and use digital tools and information efficiently in order to make well-informed decisions. Children's resilience and digital safety is their capacity to keep others and themselves safe online. Digital participation in agency is the capacity to use ICT to engage, interact, and positively impact society in an equitable manner. Digital emotional intelligence is the capacity to identify and express emotions in both intrapersonal and interpersonal digital interactions. Digital creativity and innovation is the children's capacity to express themselves and explore through the development of material utilizing ICT tools. (Pacific, 2023)
3. **21st Century Digital Citizenship Model integrates life skills with digital awareness:** (Ashutosh prabhakar & Ravindra Kumar, 2022, p. 21) emphasises on Cyber Ethics -

Responsible online behaviour, Cyber Safety - Protection against threats and Cyber Security - Protecting digital identity and data.

4. **S.A.F.E. Framework** developed to support educators as they work with students to develop their internal knowledge, skills, and capacity for understanding and applying principles of digital citizenship (*8 Digital Life Skills All Children Need - and a Plan for Teaching Them* | World Economic Forum, n.d.). The author developed the S.A.F.E. framework focusing the self-identity, engaging in positive online activities, advancing their fluency and literacy skills with digital tools demonstrating ethical decision-making in digital environments among students. This is a helpful tool for contextualizing formative instruction and the responsibilities of educators to shape student thinking for their interaction with technology locally and globally. (Kim & Choi, 2024)

Self-identity in Digital Environment (S):

This component focuses on how individuals perceive and manage their online identity, including awareness of their digital footprint and the importance of protecting personal information.

Activity in Online (A):

This aspect emphasizes engaging in positive and reasonable online activities, including respectful communication, responsible social interactions, and avoiding cyberbullying.

Fluency for Digital Environment (F):

This refers to the ability to navigate and utilize digital tools effectively, including understanding different online platforms, critical media evaluation, and adapting to new technologies.

Ethics for Digital Environment (E):

This key element focuses on upholding ethical principles online, such as respecting intellectual property, privacy concerns, and responsible online behaviour.

Significance of the SAFE model:

5. The World Economic Forum emphasizes **Digital intelligence** is a measure for the ability of an individual's command of digital media competence and The capacity to use digital media and technology in safe, responsible, and efficient ways is known as digital citizenship. Vulnerable children are more likely to be exposed to

cyberthreats such digital addiction, cyberbullying, and inappropriate exposure, which can have more serious consequences. Hence this frame work for teaching children about digital citizenship is recommended. (8 *Digital Life Skills All Children Need - and a Plan for Teaching Them* | World Economic Forum, n.d.)

There are several research studies on intersection of life skills, digital literacy, and responsible internet usage, highlighting the importance of integrating life skills training to promote digital citizenship.

“Digital Literacy and Moral Values in the Digital Environments: Secondary Students’ Perceptions,” is a study which examined secondary school students’ perceptions of moral values in digital environments and their digital literacy levels. The author suggested to foster moral values for enhancing digital literacy and promote ethical online behaviour by finding a positive correlation between moral values

and digital literacy. (Ertan Altinsoy & Serkan Boyraz, 2024)

In this study, “exploring student’s performance within a digital literacy course” students’ performance in a Digital Literacy course was examined, emphasis was given to proficiency in digital technologies for 21st-century learners. The study highlighted the significance of integrating digital literacy and essential life skills to ensure the students can use digital environments ethically and effectively. The study emphasise the importance to integrate digital literacy and life skills to ensure students to use the digital platform ethically and

effectively. (Patricia Fidalgo et al., n.d.) This is a study about “LEDUIN” a program to imparted through Instagram about digital life skills. This intervention program emphasized the importance of using social media’s for educational purpose to engage adolescents and foster digital life skills for ethical internet usage (Zimmermann & Tomczyk, 2024)

This study examined students’ use of technology both at school and at home, aiming to understand their evaluation of the education they are receiving and their ideas of 21st-century skills. It highlighted the importance of integrating life skills with digital literacy to make the students get ready for the demands of the modern world.(Mishra & Sharma, 2018)

A very recent study in Tamil Nadu on “Problematic Internet Use Among Adolescent School Attendees: A School-based Study From Tamil Nadu, India” published in national library of medicine identifies problems among adolescent due to internet usage. The study recommends for school-based intervention programs for combating these problems.(L et al., 2024)

A study aims to examine some specific behaviours in internet and its association with social connectedness, depression, and self-esteem. The study revealed the inappropriate social media usage and cyberbullying were directly related with each other. It was also found that depression was a direct predictor of problematic social media use and an indirect predictor of cyberbullying perpetration. This study acknowledges the problems due internet usage irresponsibly and the need for intervention to address this challenge.(Kýrcaburun et al., 2018)

“Impact of Exploitation of Digital World

on Gen Z” a study explores about Generation Z’s exploitation due to digital technology in Bangalore. The study examined the impact of wellbeing of GenZ due to digital exploitation. The study recommend for interventions such as policy initiatives, parental and student’s educational program, mental health awareness programs for promotion of digital responsibility for empowering Generation Z in digital environment.(Treesa, 2024)

“What It Means to be a Digital Citizen”: Using concept mapping and an educational game to explore children’s conceptualization of digital citizenship” is a study on a game-based learning on digital citizenship model to teach the children in the age group of 10-12 years. The study revealed that the children were able to conceptualize Digital Citizenship as a practice of safe, legal, and ethical behaviour and significance of digital literacy to actively participate in digital platforms after playing the online game. Hence teaching students using various experimental methods is feasible about digital citizenship is understood from this study.(Zhong & Zheng, 2023)

“Digital Citizenship and Education in India Concerning NEP 2020” a study reviewed the need for digital citizenship education and the provisions of NEP 2020. The study reviewed and recommended to provide necessary resources and infrastructure and to incorporate digital citizenship education as a part of the curriculum. the study also insisted government, educational institutions, and the private sector to collaborate and work to create awareness and organise capacity-building programs to promote digital citizenship for educators

and students. (Aman Azeem, 2023)

Understanding the prominence of Digital citizenship this study emphasises critical obligations to understand for using digital world safely. Due to the drastic development in the digital era the need for understanding digital citizenship - the roles, obligations, and abilities required to use the digital world becomes crucial. Hence Digital Citizenship Education (DCE) becomes the catalyst to result the development of efficient citizenship process. The most important aspects of digital citizenship such as examining DC, its vital aspects, ways to teach digital citizenship to young people were discussed in the study. (P.Narmatha, Dr.M.Balasubramaniam, 2023)

Firdaus & Abdulkarim from Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia made study on the topic, "Life Skills and Careers of Citizens in the Digital Age of Pancasila and Citizenship Education Curriculum Content". In this article they have studied the Pancasila and Citizenship Curriculum which prepares the students for life skills essential for pursuing their careers in the digital world. The study concludes with its findings as life and career skills strengthened by the Citizenship Education curriculum developed are important for preparing the citizens of the 21st century which is the digital era. (Firdaus Farid & Aim Abdulkarim, 2024)

Chaiyama, N., & Kaewpila, N. (2021) in the article "The Development of Life and Career Skills in 21st Century Test for Undergraduate Students" has found 6 factors which are essential skills for life and career in the 21st Century. Digital skills are found to be one among them. This article clearly explains the importance

of digital skills for the 21st Century students as one of the crucial life skill and emphasises the importance of imparting digital skills along with life skills. Hence the study support the digital skills as one of the life skill and digital citizenship can be taught using life skills. (Chaiyama & Kaewpila, 2021)

Life skills and generation Z: equipping for holistic development, suicidal engagement and post pandemic resilience by (Taylor, 2024) has published an article in George Fox university. The author drawing inspiration from biblical narrative has studied about equipping Generation Z towards positive changes. The author recommends for surviving in the post pandemic digital era, life skill trainings can incorporate versatility, emotional strength and digital literacy for them. The study exploration contributes to understand how faith and life skill training creates positive effect on the wellbeing of African diaspora. This study also supports that life skills training can provide solutions to the Gen Z for developing digital resilience and digital citizenship. (Taylor, 2024)

Tarun Deep Kaur (2011) has conducted A study on impact of life skills intervention training on emotional intelligence of college adolescents. A pre and post evaluation test was conducted to examine the effects of the life skills training to measure the changes in the level of emotional intelligence among the college students using standard testing scales. The results of the study highlighted the significant increase in the level of emotional intelligence after the training. This study clearly indicates the improvement in the level of EI among

students because of life skills training.(Kaur, 2011)

NEED FOR THE STUDY:

Cyberbullying, data privacy breaches, and misinformation are few risky online behaviours unknowingly engage by many college students. The interventions to equip students with essential life skill like coping with stress, decision-making, critical thinking becomes essential for using the digital platform wisely. This study seeks to address the growing concerns for ethical internet usage by understanding student perceptions and designing relevant training programs.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

The objective of this study is to understand the students' perceptions about the necessity of life skills training to foster and enhance digital citizenship. This study intends to assess the student's views on the importance of life skills in developing responsible and ethical behaviour while using digital technology.

METHODOLOGY

This research paper adopts a descriptive approach by using survey method to gather postgraduate social work students' perspective. A structured questionnaire was designed as the primary data collection tool. The study employed a purposive sampling technique to ensure that participants meet the specific criteria relevant to the research objectives. Students pursuing MSW were selected as the respondents of the study as they are exposed to the community through field work and may be able to represent the

general student's population. The questionnaire was forwarded to the students through google form and a total of 60 postgraduate social work students responded. The survey aimed to analyse their perspectives, experiences, and knowledge on the subject under investigation

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

A structured questionnaire was used to gather and discuss findings. The survey questionnaire was distributed among first-year MSW students in Tamil Nadu through Google Forms. Most of the responses were received from students from the Rajiv Gandhi National Institute of Youth Development and the Madras School of Social Work. A few responses were also received from Hindustan College of Arts and Science and Christ College of Arts and Science.

Distribution of Participants from various Colleges

Among the respondents, 61.7% were female and 38.3% were male. The survey received responses from 59% second-year students and 41% first-year students. A majority (88%) of the students had regular internet access, 10% used it occasionally, and a meagre of 2% rarely accessed the internet. This indicates a high prevalence of internet access among students.

Additionally, 100% of the students used smartphones, underscoring the importance of teaching the ethical usage of these devices. Nearly 24% used laptops, while a much smaller percentage (11%) used desktops and tablets.

The students were further asked about their perception of the term “responsible digital citizen.” The majority (80%) believed that using the internet safely is a key quality, followed by respecting others online (67%), reporting harmful content or behaviour (60%), and avoiding plagiarism and copyright violations (36.2%). Additionally, respondents were asked if they had received any prior training on digital literacy or related topics. Nearly 66% agreed, while 37% disagreed. With more than half of the group having knowledge of life skills training and digital literacy training, their opinions are likely to have a positive impact on the study.

Segmentation on Familiarisation of the term "Digital Citizenship" among students

Respondents were asked whether they had received any prior life skills training to inform their recommendations for life skills training for digital citizenship. Nearly 71.2% confirmed they had attended life skills training, indicating that this group was well-suited to provide opinions on this topic. When probed about their familiarity with the term “digital citizenship,” nearly 60% indicated they were somewhat familiar, while a quarter of the respondents were not aware of the term at all. The survey revealed that only 16% of students were very familiar with the term “digital literacy.”

Dispersion of students facing challenges or confusion about ethical online behaviour

Students also confirmed that more than half of 52.5% of students occasionally, 35.6% of students frequently and 12% of students face challenges or confusions about ethical online behaviours.

Digital citizenship skills	Life skills essential to develop Digital skill	Frequency		
		Very important	Somewhat important	Not important
Positive Digital Identity	Self-awareness and critical thinking	56.70%	38.70%	4.60%
Online Privacy management	Critical thinking and decision making	63.30%	28.30%	8.30%
Digital Critical thinking	Thinking skills	75%	18.30%	6.70%
Digital footprint management	Effective communication and Interpersonal skills	56.70%	38.30%	5%
Digital Empathy	Coping with emotions and stress	58.30%	33.30%	8.30%
Cyber security management	Decision making and critical thinking	70%	30%	0
Cyber bullying management	Self-awareness and critical thinking	83.10%	13.60%	11.90%
Screen time management?	Time management and self-regulation skill	52.50%	35.60%	11.90%

Students were asked to prioritize the importance of specific life skills to acquire certain digital skills. The table above describes their responses. The response from the students clearly highlights their realisation on the importance of life skills in acquiring digital citizenship skills. Majority of the responses indicate that life skills are considered very important for digital citizenship development. Nearly 56% of respondents agree that self-awareness and critical thinking are very important, and 38% feel they are somewhat important for developing a

positive digital identity. More than 60% of students believe that critical thinking and decision-making are important for developing online privacy management skills, while about 28% feel these skills are somewhat important, and only 8.3% believe they are not important. A significant majority of 75% of students believe that thinking skills are essential for developing digital critical thinking, with 18.3% feeling these skills are somewhat important, and a negligible 6.7% believing they are not important. More than half (56.7%) of students feel that effective

communication and interpersonal skills are essential for developing digital footprint management, with 38.3% considering these skills somewhat important, and only 5% believing they are not important. Nearly 58.7% of students responded that coping with emotions and stress is necessary for developing digital empathy, with 33.3% finding it somewhat important, and nearly 8% feeling it is not important. About 70% of students believe that decision-making and critical thinking skills are important for cybersecurity management, with 30% considering them somewhat important. A significant majority (83%) of students chose self-awareness and critical thinking as essential life skills for building cyberbullying management, with 13.6% finding these skills somewhat important, and 3.4% believing they are not at all important. Nearly half (52.5%) of students agree that time management and self-regulation skills are essential for screen time management, with 35.6% feeling these skills are somewhat important, and 11.9% believing they are not important. These statistics clearly demonstrate that students perceive life skills as very essential for developing digital citizenship skills.

The study also intended to know preferential mode of training about digital citizenship among students to which a

majority of 72.6 percentage of students preferred workshop mode, 50% of them preferred educational videos 37 percentage suggested group discussion, 23 percentage of students recommended online course or webinars and nearly 56.5 percentage of them preferred interactive activities for learning digital citizenship. This is very clearly shows that life skill training for digital citizenship will be an effective program to strengthen students with the essential skills for safe usage of digital platform.

Students were also asked to suggest topics on digital citizenship that should be included in the training to better understand their needs in acquiring digital citizenship skills. The results showed that:

- 80% of students recommended safe social media usage
- 75% suggested cyberbullying management and online privacy management
- 65% highlighted the need for phishing and cyber scam awareness
- 63% recommended screen time management
- 61.7% emphasized cybersecurity
- 58.3% suggested online etiquette
- 53.3% recommended digital footprint management
- 45% stressed the importance of critical thinking for evaluating online information

These findings highlight students' preferred topics for digital citizenship training. Additionally, students were asked whether the current education system adequately prepares them for responsible digital usage. While 55% agreed, 45% felt it was insufficient. Finally, students provided their suggestions on digital citizenship education, and their responses

recorded verbatim:

- “It should be conducted through workshops and other interactive programs.”
- “This is a very useful topic for students, as many people are unaware of it. Please provide knowledge on these areas.”
- “If you are discussing digital citizenship and digital footprints, I suggest also focusing on awareness and preventive measures.”
- “Be safe when using the Internet.”
- “Digital education is an essential aspect of everyone’s life and should be made mandatory in educational institutions as part of life skills training.”
- “There is a lack of digital literacy and awareness.”
- “Digital citizenship training should be integrated with life skills education to prepare students for safer and more responsible Internet usage.”

These insights reinforce the importance of structured digital citizenship education, incorporating key areas that students find most relevant and necessary.

CONCLUSION

This empirical study highlights students’ perceptions of the importance of acquiring life skills to navigate the digital landscape and equip themselves as responsible digital citizens. It also provides insights into students’ preferred mode of learning digital citizenship, with a strong preference for workshops.

Furthermore, the study identifies key topics that students consider essential, including safe social media usage, cyberbullying management, and online privacy management. These findings serve

as a needs assessment for digital citizenship training through a life skills-based approach.

The study can serve as a foundation for designing a life skills module specifically tailored to teach digital citizenship. A training program incorporating experiential learning methods—such as role plays, case studies, and student-engaging activities—can be developed to effectively equip students with essential digital citizenship skills.

IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A study (Hadi Al Ajmi et al., 2024) suggested that digital citizenship can be developed with the requisite competence by incorporating this education into schools to establish healthy digital citizenship both at home and in society. Developing a structured digital citizenship curriculum within life skills training for students ensuring that digital that all required topics are included in existing life skills programs across educational institutions is recommended.

Using experiential teaching methods like role-plays, case studies, group discussions, and real-life scenarios for making digital citizenship training engaging and incorporating gamified learning for enhancing students’ involvement to learn online safety and responsible digital behaviour. Safe social media usage, cyberbullying management, online privacy protection, and phishing awareness, could be Priority topics for the training by providing real-world examples for best practices and to enhance critical thinking for evaluating online information.

Conducting Regular Workshops and Awareness Programs on digital citizenship

in schools and colleges by engaging experts from various fields like cybersecurity, psychology, and education to provide insights on digital wellness.

Advocating to include digital citizenship training through life skills approach as part of the curriculum in schools and colleges is strongly suggested. The teachers also need to be trained to equip themselves with the necessary skills and knowledge to teach digital citizenship effectively.

Parents are also required to be educated about safe digital practices and ways to guide and guard children in online platforms. To measure the effectiveness of digital citizenship training using life skills approach pre- and post-training assessments are suggested and studied.

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